

4. GALANTON N., Provocări ale managementului lanțului de aprovizionare, Revista Economica. Chișinău: ASEM, nr.3(101), 2017, pp.7-16.
5. WATERS, D. Operations Management, Financial Times Prentice Hall, Harlow, 2002
6. WATERS, D. Global logistics. New Directions in Supply Chain Management. fifth edition, Kogan Page, London and Philadelphia, 2007
7. <https://www.americanexpress.com/en-gb/business/trends-and-insights/articles/supply-chain-mapping/> (accesat 30/04/2023)
8. <https://www.gep.com/blog/strategy/5-emerging-trends-in-supply-chain-management> (accesat 08/05/2023)
9. <https://supplychaingamechanger.com/thoughts-on-future-challenges-and-the-strategic-direction-of-supply-chain/> (accesat 01/05/2023)
10. <https://kpmg.com/xx/en/home/insights/2022/12/the-supply-chain-trends-shaking-up-2023.html> (accesat 28/04/2023)

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EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENTAL CLOUD IN DRIVING E-GOVERNANCE TRANSFORMATION

Abstract: This article explores the synergistic relationship between governmental cloud infrastructure and e-governance transformation. It examines how leveraging the capabilities of a governmental cloud can sustain the digital transformation of public services, enhance citizen engagement, and optimize administrative processes. The article presents insights, strategies, and country best practice examples to illustrate the potential impact and benefits of integrating a governmental cloud with e-governance initiatives.

Keywords: eGovernance, Digitalization of Public sector, Governmental Cloud

1. Introduction. Digital transformation in the public sector has become increasingly crucial in today's technologically advanced world. It entails leveraging digital technologies to streamline administrative processes, enhance service delivery, and improve citizen engagement. At the heart of this transformation is e-governance, which refers to the use of electronic platforms and digital tools to provide efficient and citizen-centric services.

E-governance plays a pivotal role in delivering services that are accessible, convenient, and tailored to the needs of citizens. It enables citizens to interact with government entities, access information, and avail services through online portals, mobile applications, and other digital channels. This shift towards digital service delivery not only enhances the overall citizen experience but also promotes transparency, accountability, and efficiency in public administration.

To effectively implement e-governance and harness its full potential, a robust cloud infrastructure is indispensable. Cloud computing provides the scalability, flexibility, and security required to support the complex and diverse requirements of e-governance initiatives. A robust cloud infrastructure allows for the seamless integration of various systems and databases, enabling efficient data sharing and interoperability between different government entities. It also enables the storage and processing of vast amounts of data, facilitating data-driven decision-making and personalized service delivery.

Furthermore, the cloud infrastructure accelerates the implementation of e-governance initiatives by providing the necessary computational resources, storage capacity, and networking capabilities. It eliminates the need for extensive upfront investments in hardware and infrastructure, offering a cost-effective and scalable solution. The cloud also enables rapid deployment of new services and applications, allowing governments to quickly adapt to changing citizen needs and technological advancements.

2. eGovernance's main pillars and functionality. In the context of e-governance, the pillars commonly referred to as G2C, G2G, G2B, and G2E represent the different types of interactions and relationships between the government and various stakeholders. These pillars provide a framework for organizing and implementing e-governance initiatives.

Government-to-Citizen (G2C):

The G2C pillar focuses on the delivery of government services and information directly to citizens. It involves providing online platforms, portals, and mobile applications through which citizens can access services, submit applications, make payments, and interact with government agencies. The goal is to enhance citizen convenience, increase transparency, and improve overall service delivery to citizens.

Government-to-Government (G2G):

The G2G pillar refers to the digital interactions and collaboration between different government entities. It involves the exchange of information, sharing of resources, and coordination of activities among government agencies and departments. G2G initiatives aim to streamline administrative processes, improve data sharing and interoperability, and enhance interdepartmental collaboration for effective governance.

Government-to-Business (G2B):

The G2B pillar focuses on the digital interactions between the government and businesses. It involves providing online platforms and services that enable businesses to interact with government agencies for various purposes, such as obtaining licenses, permits, and certifications, submitting tax returns, accessing

procurement opportunities, and participating in government programs. G2B initiatives aim to streamline business-government interactions, reduce bureaucracy, and facilitate a conducive business environment.

Government-to-Employee (G2E):

The G2E pillar relates to the digital interactions between the government and its employees. It involves providing digital platforms and tools for government employees to access information, manage their employment details, apply for leave, access training and development resources, and participate in internal communication and collaboration. G2E initiatives aim to enhance employee productivity, engagement, and satisfaction while promoting efficient workforce management within the government.

Table 1 provides a concise overview of each pillar, and further details and subtopics can be explored within each pillar to fully understand their significance in the e-governance context.

Table 1 – The representation of the e-governance pillars and subtopics

Pillar	Description	Subtopics
Government-to-Citizen (G2C)	Delivery of government services and information to citizens	Online portals, Mobile applications, Service accessibility, Digital identity systems
Government-to-Government (G2G)	Collaboration and information sharing among government entities	Interdepartmental data sharing, Shared services, Collaboration platforms, Government network infrastructure
Government-to-Business (G2B)	Digital interactions between government and businesses	Online business registration, e-Procurement systems, Business licensing and permits, Digital tax filing
Government-to-Employee (G2E)	Digital tools and platforms for government employee management	HR management systems, Employee self-service portals, Training and development platforms, Internal communication tools

The pillars (table 1) represent the different dimensions of e-governance and highlight the diverse stakeholders involved in the digital transformation of government services. By focusing on these pillars, governments can tailor their e-governance strategies and initiatives to meet the specific needs of citizens, businesses, government agencies, and employees, ultimately leading to more effective and citizen-centric service delivery.

3. Governmental Cloud, definition and description. The Governmental Cloud is also known as GovCloud or Government Cloud and is considered a specialized cloud computing infrastructure designed to meet the unique requirements of the public sector. It provides government agencies, ministries, and other public institutions with a secure and scalable platform to store, process, and access data and applications. This technology enables governments to leverage the benefits of

cloud computing while ensuring data sovereignty, privacy, and compliance with regulatory frameworks.

The main cloud deployment models could be the fundament for Governmental Cloud and the main features of each are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – The classic cloud models

Source:

[https://chmura.gov.pl/zuch/static/media/Cloud%20in%20Government%20Services_Final%20\[ENG\].pdf](https://chmura.gov.pl/zuch/static/media/Cloud%20in%20Government%20Services_Final%20[ENG].pdf)

In Figure 1, the description of each model is presented below:

1. A public cloud is operated by third party providers who pool their infrastructure to provide shared (yet segregated) services to multiple customers (multi-tenants).

2. These are cloud based resources that are used exclusively by a single organization, with the infrastructure or services maintained via a private network.

3. This is a multi-tenant platform that is accessible only for a specific subset of customers and is designed to meet the common needs of those users.

4. Hybrid cloud solutions use a mix of two or more cloud models (e.g.private cloud, public cloud services and community cloud) in a way which enables data to be shared between them.

The key features and benefits of implementing a Governmental Cloud are presented below:

Enhanced Data Security: Governmental Cloud incorporates robust security measures to protect sensitive government data. It utilizes advanced encryption, access controls, and monitoring systems to safeguard against unauthorized access and cyber threats.

Improved Efficiency and Cost Savings: By centralizing IT infrastructure and services, Governmental Cloud promotes resource optimization and cost

efficiencies. It eliminates the need for individual agencies to maintain separate data centers, resulting in reduced operational costs and streamlined IT management.

Scalability and Flexibility: The cloud infrastructure allows government agencies to scale their resources according to demand. They can quickly provision additional storage, computing power, or applications as needed, enabling agile and responsive service delivery.

Collaboration and Interoperability: Governmental Cloud facilitates seamless data sharing and collaboration among government agencies. It enables interoperability between different systems and promotes standardized data formats and interfaces, leading to improved efficiency and coordination.

Citizen-Centric Services: With Governmental Cloud, governments can deliver citizen-centric digital services, such as online portals and mobile applications. This empowers citizens to conveniently access government information, avail services, and engage in participatory governance.

Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity: Governmental Cloud offers robust disaster recovery capabilities, ensuring data backup, redundancy, and continuity in the event of natural disasters or system failures. It enables quick recovery and minimizes service disruptions.

Governmental Cloud is a powerful tool that enables digital transformation in the public sector. It provides a secure, scalable, and cost-effective infrastructure for governments to deliver efficient, citizen-centric services, foster collaboration, and enhance data security. By harnessing the benefits of cloud computing, governments can streamline operations, drive innovation, and achieve their digital governance objectives. Governmental Cloud represents a crucial step toward building modern, resilient, and technology-driven governments that cater to the needs of citizens in the digital age.

4. European countries that can be used as best practice in eGovernment domain. Below are presented some examples of European countries and how they combine governmental cloud infrastructure with e-governance to achieve a digital transformation.

Estonia is recognized as a leader in e-governance and has implemented a robust governmental cloud infrastructure called "X-Road"¹. It serves as the backbone for various e-governance initiatives, enabling secure data exchange between government agencies and providing a platform for digital services. For example, citizens can access their health records, file taxes, vote online, and even start businesses within minutes. The governmental cloud infrastructure ensures data security and privacy while facilitating seamless collaboration and interoperability among different government departments.

The United Kingdom has made significant strides in combining governmental cloud infrastructure and e-governance transformation. The government has adopted a "Cloud First" policy, encouraging public sector organizations to use cloud services. The Government Digital Service (GDS) has

¹ <https://x-road.global/x-road-technology-overview>

led initiatives such as Gov.uk, a centralized portal offering a wide range of digital services to citizens. The cloud infrastructure supports these services, ensuring scalability, cost optimization, and efficient data management across various government agencies.

Denmark has implemented a robust governmental cloud infrastructure called "NemLog-in"¹ to support its e-governance initiatives. The platform provides citizens with a single digital identity for accessing multiple government services. It enables secure authentication, data sharing, and collaboration across different government entities. The cloud infrastructure ensures data security, scalability, and interoperability, facilitating efficient e-governance processes and personalized service delivery.

Finland has embraced e-governance transformation and leveraged cloud infrastructure to enhance service delivery. The "Suomi.fi" platform serves as a centralized digital hub for citizens, offering access to various public services. The cloud infrastructure enables seamless integration and interoperability of services from different government agencies. Citizens can access personal data, apply for permits, and communicate with government entities through a single digital interface, simplifying their interactions with the government.

The Netherlands has adopted a cloud-first strategy for its e-governance initiatives. The government has established the "DigiCloud" platform, which provides cloud infrastructure and services for government agencies. It promotes interoperability, data sharing, and collaboration across departments. The cloud infrastructure supports various e-governance applications, such as online tax filing, citizen portals, and digital identity services, enhancing convenience and efficiency for citizens.

These examples demonstrate how European countries have successfully integrated governmental cloud infrastructure with e-governance transformation. By leveraging secure and scalable cloud platforms, these countries have improved service delivery, promoted citizen engagement, and achieved operational efficiencies in their governance systems. The combination of cloud infrastructure and e-governance initiatives has enabled them to provide seamless, citizen-centric services while ensuring data security, privacy, and interoperability across government agencies.

5. Conclusions. The synergistic relationship between governmental cloud infrastructure and e-governance transformation is instrumental in driving effective and citizen-centric governance. The cloud infrastructure serves as the foundation, providing the necessary resources, scalability, and security for e-governance initiatives to thrive. At the same time, e-governance leverages the capabilities of the cloud to deliver efficient, personalized, and accessible services to citizens.

By combining the power of governmental cloud infrastructure and e-governance transformation, governments can achieve the following:

¹ <https://digst.dk/>

Improved Service Delivery: The cloud enables governments to streamline service delivery processes, automate workflows, and provide citizens with seamless access to services anytime, anywhere. This results in enhanced convenience, efficiency, and satisfaction for citizens.

Enhanced Collaboration and Data Sharing: The cloud facilitates seamless data sharing and interoperability between government departments, promoting collaboration and enabling better-informed decision-making. It breaks down silos, enabling a holistic and integrated approach to governance.

Agility and Innovation: The cloud's scalability and flexibility allow governments to quickly adapt to changing needs, deploy new services, and experiment with innovative solutions. It enables rapid development, testing, and iteration of e-governance initiatives, fostering continuous improvement and innovation.

Cost Optimization: By leveraging shared cloud infrastructure and resources, governments can optimize costs associated with IT infrastructure and maintenance. This frees up resources that can be redirected towards improving public services and investing in further digital transformation.

Citizen Engagement and Empowerment: E-governance initiatives, supported by the cloud, empower citizens by providing them with digital platforms to engage with the government, voice their opinions, and actively participate in decision-making processes. It strengthens the relationship between citizens and the government, fostering transparency, trust, and accountability.

In conclusion, the integration of governmental cloud infrastructure and e-governance transformation is vital for governments aiming to deliver efficient, citizen-centric, and digitally enabled governance. Estonia is a good example than can be followed by any nation that intends to digitalize the public sector. The steps of how they have built a digital society are presented at this link <https://e-estonia.com/>. This collaboration enables governments to leverage the scalability, security, and cost efficiencies of the cloud while harnessing the transformative potential of e-governance. Together, they lay the foundation for a modern, transparent, and inclusive governance system that meets the needs and expectations of citizens in the digital era.

6. References

1. *** Chapter 13. Case Study 8: Estonia e-government and the creation of a comprehensive data infrastructure for public services and agriculture policies implementation, <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/510a82b5-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/510a82b5-en#wrapper> accessed in April 2023
Nielsen, M., & Yasouka, M. (2014). An analysis of the Danish approach to eGovernment benefit realisation. *Internet Technologies and Society 2014*, 47-58.
2. *** Digital Government Factsheet 2019 Finland, https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/inline-files/Digital_Government_Factsheets_Finland_2019.pdf, accessed in March 2023

3. Al Mudawi, N., Beloff, N., & White, M. (2020). Issues and challenges: Cloud computing e-government in developing countries. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(4), 7-11.
4. Alshehri, M., & Drew, S. (2010). Implementation of e-government: advantages and challenges. In *International Association for Scientific Knowledge (IASK)*.
5. Osifo, O.C., (2018). Examining digital government and public service provision : the case of Finland. In: 2018 41st International Convention on Information and Communication Technology, Electronics and Microelectronics (MIPRO), Opatija, 2018 (pp. 1342–1347). <https://doi.org/10.23919/MIPRO.2018.8400242>
*** E-Democracy, E-Governance And Public Sector Reform Revisited – Experiences of The Main Themes of the PADOS project in Finland and Estonia, https://um.fi/documents/35732/48132/e_democracy__e_governance_and_public_sector_reform_revisited___experiences_of, accessed in March 2023
- Alvarenga, A., Matos, F., Godina, R., & CO Matias, J. (2020). Digital transformation and knowledge management in the public sector. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5824.
6. Sarikas, O. D., & Weerakkody, V. (2007). Realising integrated e-government services: a UK local government perspective. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 1(2), 153-173.
7. Weerakkody, V., & Choudrie, J. (2005). Exploring e-government in the UK: Challenges, issues and complexities. *Journal of Information Science & Technology*, 2(2).
8. Zakrzewska, M., & Miciuła, I. (2021). Using e-government services and ensuring the protection of sensitive data in EU member countries. *Procedia Computer Science*, 192, 3457-3466.
9. Zwattendorfer, B., & Tauber, A. (2013). The public cloud for e-government. *International Journal of Distributed Systems and Technologies (IJDST)*, 4(4), 1-14.
10. Zwattendorfer, B., Stranacher, K., Tauber, A., & Reichstädter, P. (2013). Cloud computing in E-government across Europe: a comparison. In *Technology-Enabled Innovation for Democracy, Government and Governance: Second Joint International Conference on Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective, and Electronic Democracy, EGOVIS/EDEM 2013, Prague, Czech Republic, August 26-28, 2013, Proceedings 2* (pp. 181-195). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.